

Influence of dielectric constant on chemical speciation of Ca^{II}, Zn^{II} and Mn^{II} with L-valine

B. Veeraswami^a, G. Nageswara Rao^{*b} and U. Viplavaprasad^b

^aGitam Institute of Technology, Gitam University, Visakhapatnam-530 045, Andhra Pradesh, India

^bSchool of Chemistry, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam-530 003, Andhra Pradesh, India

E-mail : gollapallinr@yahoo.com

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Abstract : The titrations are carried out with sodium hydroxide in varying concentrations (0–60% v/v) of propylene glycol-water mixtures at ionic strength of 0.16 mol L⁻¹ and temperature 303 K. Models containing different number of species were refined by using the computer program MINIQUAD75. The species ML⁺, MLH²⁺ and ML₂H⁺ were chosen based on exhaustive modeling studies. The best-fit chemical models were arrived at based on statistical parameters. The linear increase in the stability of the complexes with decreasing dielectric constant of the medium indicates the dominance of electrostatic forces in the equilibrium process under the present experimental conditions. The order of the stabilities of the complexes is Ca^{II} < Mn^{II} < Zn^{II}. The species distribution and the feasible equilibria for the formation of the species are also presented.

Keywords : Chemical speciation, L-valine, propylene glycol, MINIQUAD75.

Introduction

Chemical speciation of metals is important for an understanding of their distribution, mobility, bioavailability, toxicity and for setting environmental quality standards^{1–3}. For this, it is essential to determine the speciation of metal complexes of biological importance at low dielectric constant of the medium, which mimics the biofluids. Hence the title systems were studied in the presence of propylene glycol (PG), which decreases the dielectric constant of the medium⁴. It is metabolized into pyruvic acid, acetic acid, lactic acid⁵ and a highly toxic substance, propionaldehyde⁶. PG also acts as a mild anesthetic/CNS-depressant⁷.

Recently chemical speciation of amino acids with essential metal ions like Ca^{II}, Zn^{II} and Mn^{II} was studied in different media^{8–10}. L-Valine is non-polar essential amino acid having wide applications in pharmaceutical and food industries¹¹. Formation of binary complexes of L-valine with some essential metals was reported by potentiometric^{12,13} and paper electrophoretic techniques¹⁴. Their stability constants were evaluated with the aid of computer program SCOGS¹⁵. The protonation constants of L-valine were determined in propylene glycol (PG)-water mixtures¹⁶.

Experimental

Materials and solutions :

Solutions 0.05 mol L⁻¹ of L-valine (SRL, India, 99%), 0.10 mol L⁻¹ Ca^{II}, Zn^{II} and Mn^{II} chlorides (Qualigens, India, A.R. grade) were prepared in triple distilled water by maintaining 0.05 mol L⁻¹ hydrochloric acid concentration to increase the solubility. Propylene glycol (Qualigens, India) was used without further purification. Carbonate free sodium hydroxide (Qualigens, India) pellets were used for the preparation of 0.40 mol L⁻¹ solution. Hydrochloric acid (Qualigens, India) of 0.20 mol L⁻¹ was prepared. 2.0 mol L⁻¹ of sodium chloride (Qualigens, India) was prepared to maintain 0.16 mol L⁻¹ ionic strength in the titrand. The strengths of acid and alkali were determined using Gran plot method¹⁷. To assess the errors that might have crept in to the determination of the concentrations, the data were subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification ANOVA¹⁸.

Apparatus :

The titrimetric data were obtained by Systronics MK-VI (Readability 0.01) digital pH meter was used. It is calibrated with potassium hydrogen phthalate (0.050 mol

L⁻¹) in acidic region and borax (0.010 mol L⁻¹) solution in basic region. The glass electrode was equilibrated in a well stirred PG-water mixture containing inert electrolyte for several days. All the titrations were carried out in the medium containing varying compositions of PG (0.0–60.0% v/v) maintaining an ionic strength of 0.160 mol L⁻¹ with sodium chloride at 303.0 ± 0.1 K. The effect of variations in asymmetry potential, liquid junction potential, activity coefficient, sodium ion error and dissolved carbon dioxide on the response of glass electrode were accounted for in the form of correction factor¹⁹.

Procedure :

For the determination of stability constants of metal-L-valine binary species, initially titrations of strong acid with alkali were carried out at regular intervals to check the complete equilibrium of the glass electrode. Then the calomel electrode was refilled with PG-water mixture of equivalent composition as that of titrand. In each of the titrations, the titrand consisted of approximately 1 mmol mineral acid in a total volume of 50.0 mL. Titrations with different ratios (1 : 2.5, 1 : 3.75 and 1 : 5.0) of metal-to-valine were carried out with 0.40 mol L⁻¹ sodium hydroxide²⁰. The details of the experimental procedure and titration assembly have been detailed elsewhere²¹.

Modeling strategy :

The computer program SCPHD²² was used to calculate the correction factor. The binary stability constants of metal-valine were calculated by using the pH-metric titration data using computer program, MINIQUAD75²³ which exploits the advantage of constrained least-squares method in the initial refinement and reliable convergence of Marquardt algorithm. During the refinement of binary systems, the correction factor and protonation constants of L-valine (Table 1) were fixed.

Table 1. Protonation constants of L-valine in PG-water mixtures

% v/v PG	Dielectric constant of PG-water mixture	log β ₁	log β ₂
0.0	78.54	9.41	11.70
10.0	75.44	9.36	11.84
20.0	71.18	9.46	12.13
30.0	65.69	9.56	12.25
40.0	61.0	9.46	12.22
50.0	56.40	9.54	12.44
60.0	51.24	9.50	12.66

Results and discussion

Exhaustive modeling was performed for all the systems in various compositions of the solvent mixtures to identify the most probable species that may form the best fit model. The results of a typical system are given in Table 2. The models indicate better statistics as the number of species was increased, confirming better fit. There was no further improvement in the fit on inclusion of some more species in the model containing CaL, CaLH and CaL₂H. This indicates that the final model appropriately fit the experimental data.

The present results are comparable with those reported in the literature for L-valine^{24,25} as given in Table 3. The results of the best fit models that contain the stoichiometry of the complex species and their overall formation constants, along with some of the important statistical parameters are given in Table 4. The low standard deviation in overall stability constants (log β) signifies the precision of these constants. The small values of *U*_{corr}, small values of the mean, standard deviation and mean deviation for the systems are validated by the residual analysis.

Residual analysis :

In data analysis with least squares methods, the residuals are assumed to follow Gaussian distribution. When the data are fit into the models, the residuals should be ideally equal to zero. Further, a model is considered adequate only if the residuals do not show any trend. Respecting the hypothesis of the least squares analysis, the residuals are tested for normal distribution. Such tests are χ², skewness, kurtosis and *R*-factor. The best-fit model is selected using the statistical parameters²⁶ of the least squares residuals of metal-L-valine complexes in PG-water mixtures.

The values of skewness recorded in Table 4 are between -1.66 and 2.79 for Ca^{II}, 0.29 and 1.07 for Zn^{II} and -1.33 and 0.83 for Mn^{II}. The kurtosis values for Ca^{II}, Zn^{II} and Mn^{II} in the present study indicate that the residuals form a leptokurtic and platykurtic pattern. The χ² values are in the range 6.40 to 79.41 for different number of points and all of them are less than the table values. The pH meter readability (0.01) was taken as the *R*_{lim} and all the crystallographic *R* values given in Table 4 are less than the *R*_{lim}. These data supports the

Table 2. Exhaustive modeling study performed on Ca^{II}-valine system in 30% v/v PG-water mixture
pH range = 1.8–10.8, NP = 40

Model number	log β _{mlh} (SD)			U _{corr} × 10 ⁸	χ ²	Skewness	Kurtosis	R-factor
	ML	MLH	ML ₂ H					
1	1.77 (17)	–	–	5.02	76.0	–1.29	4.17	0.0098
2	–	11.68 (13)	–	3.81	42.93	0.26	4.76	0.0085
3	–	–	13.91 (22)	5.10	60.40	–1.24	4.06	0.0099
4	2.77 (8)	12.10 (6)	–	1.04	51.87	–0.41	4.29	0.0044
5	–	12.05 (8)	15.01 (15)	1.84	49.73	1.06	9.33	0.0059
6	1.71 (21)	–	13.62 (20)	4.97	69.87	–1.31	4.24	0.0098
7	2.74 (9)	12.10 (6)	14.28 (18)	0.99	53.07	–0.47	4.46	0.0043

U_{corr} = U/(NP – m); m = number of species; NP = number of experimental points; SD = standard deviation.

Table 3. Comparison of the results of stepwise binary stability constants of L-valine complexes with literature values

Metal ion	Species	Present value	Literature value	Ref.
Ca ^{II}	ML	2.43	–	–
	MLH	11.41	–	–
	ML ₂ H	14.05	–	–
Zn ^{II}	ML	5.08	4.44	24
	MLH	11.66	–	–
	ML ₂ H	16.53	–	–
Mn ^{II}	ML	3.06	3.77	25
	MLH	11.50	–	–
	ML ₂ H	14.74	–	–

residuals form a normal distribution and hence, the least squares method can be applied to the present study.

Effect of systematic errors on best fit model :

Any variation in the concentrations of ingredients affects the magnitudes of stability constants. Such parameters are called influential parameters. In order to rely upon the best fit chemical model for critical evaluation and application under varied experimental conditions with different accuracies of data acquisition, Zn^{II}-valine system in 30% v/v PG-water mixture was studied by introducing the errors in the concentrations of ingredients (like mineral acid, ligand, metal and alkali and log *F*). The

Table 4. Parameters of the best-fit chemical models of L-valine complexes of Ca^{II}, Zn^{II} and Mn^{II} in PG-water mixtures

Temperature = 303 K, Ionic strength = 0.16 mol L⁻¹

% v/v PG	log β _{mlh} (SD)			NP	U _{corr} Ca ^{II}	Skewness	χ ²	Kurtosis	R-factor	pH-range
	ML	MLH	ML ₂ H							
0.0	2.43 (47)	11.41 (45)	14.05 (52)	36	21.11	–0.15	79.41	4.22	0.0406	2.8–10.6
10.0	1.82 (37)	11.67 (15)	13.80 (64)	50	5.89	2.79	63.41	19.84	0.0113	1.8–10.8
20.0	2.72 (15)	11.46 (8)	14.42 (54)	41	1.02	0.69	30.56	4.51	0.0042	1.8–10.8
30.0	2.74 (9)	12.10 (6)	14.35 (71)	40	0.99	–0.46	48.00	4.43	0.0043	1.8–10.8
40.0	2.84 (23)	12.52 (14)	14.83 (98)	33	13.77	–1.66	34.09	7.25	0.0204	1.8–10.8
50.0	3.31 (15)	11.98 (12)	14.69 (10)	43	3.09	–0.36	23.74	3.39	0.0077	1.8–10.8
60.0	3.77 (17)	12.91 (13)	15.17 (67)	55	10.58	1.41	17.64	7.29	0.0127	1.8–10.8
					Zn ^{II}					
0.0	5.08 (41)	11.66 (13)	16.53 (19)	45	6.83	0.29	11.79	3.54	0.0094	1.6–8.6
10.0	5.69 (59)	11.30 (21)	17.08 (45)	46	7.86	1.07	10.0	10.30	0.0102	1.5–8.6
20.0	5.62 (32)	12.55 (10)	17.44 (56)	39	5.64	0.45	15.85	4.04	0.0122	1.5–8.6
30.0	6.06 (30)	12.65 (8)	17.56 (16)	43	3.51	0.59	15.93	6.76	0.0079	1.5–8.6
40.0	6.53 (44)	13.14 (15)	18.06 (50)	40	8.05	0.67	14.00	3.82	0.0144	1.5–8.6
50.0	6.51 (62)	13.05 (20)	18.16 (58)	40	16.81	0.42	6.40	2.61	0.0209	1.5–8.6
60.0	6.40 (47)	12.96 (16)	17.97 (50)	39	10.51	0.47	6.97	3.03	0.0165	1.5–8.6

Table-4 (contd.)

					Mn ^{II}					
0.0	3.06 (16)	11.50 (5)	14.74 (19)	44	0.60	-0.02	46.02	17.00	0.0027	1.6-9.0
10.0	3.62 (11)	11.84 (3)	15.29 (27)	45	4.06	0.77	23.99	6.36	0.0027	1.5-9.2
20.0	3.69 (37)	12.22 (13)	15.53 (22)	37	3.88	-1.33	22.41	7.15	0.0099	1.5-9.2
30.0	4.71 (45)	12.13 (14)	16.36 (22)	39	3.37	-0.06	23.24	3.76	0.0095	1.5-9.2
40.0	4.61 (28)	12.86 (12)	15.82 (84)	47	3.80	0.62	12.48	2.87	0.0070	1.5-9.2
50.0	5.61 (36)	13.19 (13)	17.09 (81)	39	7.97	0.83	30.21	2.73	0.0142	1.5-9.2
60.0	6.26 (90)	13.63 (17)	18.19 (78)	38	6.13	0.57	17.37	2.73	0.0126	1.5-9.2

order of the ingredients that influence the magnitudes of stability constants due to incorporation of errors is alkali > acid > ligand > log F > metal. Some species were even rejected when errors were introduced in the concentrations. The rejection of some species and increased standard deviations in the stability constants on introduction of errors confirm the suitability of the experimental conditions (concentrations of ingredients) and choice of the best fit models. These results (Table 5) emphasize that errors in the concentrations of alkali and acid affect more than other factors.

Table 5. Effect of errors in influential parameters on the stability constants of Zn^{II}-valine complexes in 30% v/v of PG-water mixtures

Ingredient	% Error	log β_{mlh} (SD)		
		ML	MLH	ML ₂ H
Alkali	0	5.08 (41)	11.66 (13)	16.53 (19)
	-5	Rejected	Rejected	15.78 (44)
	-2	5.32 (26)	12.23 (13)	Rejected
	+2	7.02 (33)	12.94 (11)	Rejected
	+5	9.12 (10)	13.19 (4)	20.03 (28)
Acid	-5	9.42 (16)	14.02 (5)	20.18 (37)
	-2	7.67 (39)	13.63 (26)	Rejected
	+2	4.82 (22)	10.84 (38)	Rejected
	+5	Rejected	Rejected	15.90 (48)
	Ligand	-5	5.84 (21)	12.21 (10)
-2		6.04 (18)	12.48 (8)	Rejected
+2		6.31 (21)	12.81 (8)	Rejected
+5		6.55 (21)	13.06 (10)	Rejected
Metal		-5	6.28 (23)	12.70 (9)
	-2	6.21 (22)	12.67 (9)	Rejected
	+2	6.13 (21)	12.62 (8)	Rejected
	+5	6.08 (17)	12.59 (7)	Rejected
	log F	-5	6.38 (22)	12.87 (9)
-2		6.25 (22)	12.73 (8)	Rejected
+2		6.10 (19)	12.56 (8)	Rejected
+5		5.99 (21)	12.43 (8)	Rejected

Effect of dielectric constant :

PG is an amphiprotic and coordinating solvent. It removes water from coordination sphere of metal ions, making them more reactive towards the ligands. As a result, the stability of the complexes is expected to increase. At the same time, it is a coordinating solvent and competes with the ligands for coordinating the metals. This decreases the stability of the complexes. Hence the stability of the complex is expected to either increase or decrease. Variation of logarithmic values of stability constants (log β) or change in free energy with co-solvent content depends upon two factors, viz. electrostatic and non-electrostatic. Born's classical treatment²⁷ holds good in accounting for the electrostatic contribution to the free energy change. According to this statement, the energy of electrostatic interaction is related to dielectric constant. Hence, the log β values should vary linearly as a function of the reciprocal of the dielectric constant (D) of the medium, which is observed in the present study (Fig. 1). The linear trend indicates that electrostatic forces are dominating the equilibrium process under the present experimental conditions.

Distribution diagrams :

L-Valine is a bidentate ligand that has one associable and one dissociable protons. It exist as LH₂⁺ at lower pH (1.5-4.0) and on deprotonation to form species LH and L⁻ successively in the pH ranges, 4.0-9.0 and 9.0-11.0 respectively. The present investigation reveals the existence of ML, MLH, and ML₂H for Ca^{II}, Zn^{II} and Mn^{II}. The stability constants of these species are found to follow the trend Ca^{II} < Mn^{II} < Zn^{II}. This is in conformity with the Mellor-Maley's order^{28,29}. This trend is justified based on the nature of the three metal ions. Ca^{II} ion has inert gas configuration and Zn^{II} ion has pseudo inert gas configuration. Hence according to Hard and Soft Acid

Fig. 1. Variation of stability constants of metal-valine complexes with $1/D$ of PG-water mixtures : (A) Ca^{II} , (B) Zn^{II} , (C) Mn^{II} ; (■) $\log \beta_{\text{ML}}$, (●) $\log \beta_{\text{MLH}}$, (▲) $\log \beta_{\text{ML}_2\text{H}}$.

Base theory, Zn^{II} ion forms more stable complexes than Ca^{II} ion. Mn^{II} ion has half filled d sublevel and so forms both low spin and high spin complexes. Hence Zn^{II} forms more stable complexes than Mn^{II} ion.

The formation of various metal-valine complex species is shown in the following equilibria.

Species distribution of ML^+ , MLH^{2+} and ML_2H^+ (Fig. 2) are formed in the pH range 1.8–10.8 for Ca^{II} , 1.5–8.6 for Zn^{II} and 1.5–9.2 for Mn^{II} . For all metal-ligand systems, MLH^{2+} species is formed by the interac-

Fig. 2. Species distribution diagrams of L-valine complexes of (A) Ca^{II} , (B) Zn^{II} and (C) Mn^{II} in 30% v/v, PG-water mixtures.

tion of metal ion with LH_2^+ (Equilibrium 1), where the percentages of FM and LH_2^+ are decreasing with increasing percentage of MLH^{2+} . Deprotonation of MLH^{2+} to ML^+ species (Equilibrium 2) and the interaction of FM with LH to form ML^+ species (Equilibrium 3). But Equilibrium 2 is more predominant than Equilibrium 3, because the concentration of FM decreases while concentration of LH increases with pH. And ML_2H^+ species is formed in Equilibria 4 and 5. But Equilibrium 4 is predominant than Equilibrium 5, because the concentration of MLH^{2+} and LH are decreasing with increasing concentration of ML_2H^+ .

Conclusions

- (i) L-Valine forms both protonated and unprotonated species in the pH range 1.5–10.8.
- (ii) The predicted binary species of L-valine are ML, MLH and ML_2H which are validated by statistical data.
- (iii) The linear trend indicates that the dielectric constant (D) or long range interactions are responsible for the stability trend. This linear increase indicates the dominance of the structure-forming nature of PG over its complexing ability.
- (iv) The order of the ingredients that influence the magnitudes of stability constants is alkali > acid > ligand > metal > log F .
- (v) The stability constants of binary complexes are found to follow the trend $\text{Ca}^{\text{II}} < \text{Mn}^{\text{II}} < \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$ in PG-water mixtures.

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